

Joint workshop

LIFE RIPARIAS / LIFE MICA

Towards a data standard for reporting on IAS management interventions

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Towards a data standard for reporting on IAS management interventions

25 march 2022, 9:30-13:00 CET

Online participation link:

<https://bruxelles-environnement.webex.com/bruxelles-environnement/j.php?MTID=maae17d0172746ec32363e9a124e7dbb2>

Aims

- To work actively towards the development of a data standard for reporting on management which could be presented at the upcoming TDWG¹ conference in October 2022 (TDWG is a world organization maintaining Biodiversity Information Standards)
- To gather insight for developing the management reporting system (Action A.2.2 Develop a system to report on management actions & effectiveness) within the Belgian RIPARIAS project²
- To share good practices & ideas on monitoring / reporting on management of IAS of Union Concern

Outputs

- kick-start a longer term process towards the development of a data exchange format for management reporting ratified by an international Biodiversity Information Standards organisation (TDWG)
- A jointly drafted discussion paper describing a prototype standard to exchange information on wildlife management (focusing on Union List IAS). This paper will provide the framework for collaboration with all contributors (co-authors selected from standard development, use cases, field managers)
 - Initial proposal for standard v0.1 (lead by INBO)
 - Workshop to review initial proposal, gather feedback and use case
 - Create standard v0.2
 - Present standard v0.2 at TDWG (October 2022)
 - Create standard v0.3

Contact

For all questions regarding the workshop organisation, don't hesitate to contact us by e-mail at riparias@environnement.brussels

¹ <https://www.tdwg.org/>

² <https://www.riparias.be/>

Agenda

TIME	TOPIC	SPEAKER
09:30	Welcome & Round table	
09:40	Introductory talk The need for a data exchange format on IAS / wildlife management and the trajectory towards an adopted standard, including preview of some existing data standards (Darwin Core ³ , camtrapdp ⁴) Q&A	Damiano Oldoni, Life RIPARIAS
10:30	IAS management and data collection use cases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management activities, reporting and data flows in LIFE RIPARIAS • The Enetwild standard for reporting on wildlife management and data exchange between Member States • Management activities, reporting and data flows in American mink control in Charente and Charente-Maritime • Management activities, reporting and data flows in American mink control on French Overseas Territories • A provisional template for reporting IAS management in Life projects 	Emma Cartuyvels, Life MICA Joaquin Vicente & Guillaume Body, Enetwild Ingrid Marchand, Life VISON Delphine Morin, Life BIODIV'OM Riccardo Scalera, IUCN ISSG
11 :30	Introduction to break out + break-outs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IAS Plant management - terrestrial and aquatic • Trapping - terrestrial and semi-aquatic (rodents, squirrels and other mammals, birds...) • Trapping - aquatic (e.g. sliders, crayfish, amphibians, fish...) • Shooting and hunting (mammals, birds) 	
12:00	Plenary session to discuss all ideas together	
12 :45	Closing remarks & next steps	

³ tdwg.org/standards/dwc/

⁴ <https://tdwg.github.io/camtrap-dp/>

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